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TEACHING EXPERIMENT AND RESEARCH OF VISUAL STORY NARRATION DESIGN

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ABSTRACT

The popularity of story-telling in design has made it indispensable in the training of college design students. Based on the knowledge of emotional design, scenarios, and the psychology of reception, this research aims to help young designers create visual stories through an understanding of the processes involved in story-making with practical experience in applying various tips. We adopted the research method of teaching experiment, consensus assessment techniques, and evaluation of learning satisfaction, eventually proving that students participating in the experiment outperformed the control students in most of criteria associated with communication and emotional response from ads. The results of the teaching experiment using creative design tips on story-making reference cards could help other young designers to present visual storyness in product design and advertisements, as a means to impress audiences with unique and interesting experiences in developing lasting impressions.

Keywords: visual story narration, emotional design, teaching experiment.

INTRODUCTION

A major challenge faced by contemporary product designers is the need to make their products stand out from the crowd, amid a chaos of information overload. Creative design, unique marketing ideas, and aesthetic economy are indispensable in product design. Among these strategies, story-telling and emphasizing the emotional memory and symbolic

value of customers are the most important weapons in any marketing arsenal. Passing through the industrial revolution, post-capitalism, and the global network village, the value of "objects" has evolved from simple usage and exchange value to become symbols of social status and fashion trends. The importance of emotional value has surpassed that of symbolic value following recent financial crises and energy conservation.

Donald A. Norman, the well known cognitive psychologist, claimed that, "A favorite object is a symbol, setting up a positive frame of mind, a reminder of pleasant memories, or sometimes an expression of one's self. And this object always has a story, a remembrance, and something that ties us personally to this particular object, this particular thing." (Norman, 2004)

Rolf Jensen (2000), the author of "The Dream Society: How the Coming Shift from Information to Imagination Will Transform Your Business", mentioned that, instead of over-emphasizing function and technology, a more important and comparable advantage associated with commodities is the "story", which inspires consumers and increases their willingness to purchase.

HYPOTHESIS OF RESEARCH

Based on the above background, we presume that the features of a visual narrative story could help graphics designers to create more convincing advertisements, by eliciting in readers a sense of curiosity, and inspiring a positive impression. This

hypothesis assumes that to create a visually narrated story in advertisements, students could obtain ideas from experimental models in which story-making reference cards provide a step-by-step process to stimulate a richer and more diverse presentation.

LITERATURE REVIEW

SCENARIO APPROACH

Scenarios are commonly employed in the process of product design. In this approach, the characteristics of users, relevant events, and the relationships among products and the environment are used to explore the concept behind the design of products by imaginatively describing future scenarios. The scenario approach, also known as script guidance, refers to the writing procedure of literature –opening, developing, changing and concluding. An analysis of lifestyle, technology, social trends, and market positioning, SWOT analysis, and user characteristics, provides the designer with the background knowledge required to develop the context and interactive models. Such "user-oriented" designs adopt this approach in visual plots, by modeling "people, time, places, events, and objects (products)" to break the ice at the beginning of brainstorming (Tang & Kang, 2008).

Nielsen (1990) established eight categories with regard to the application of the scenario approach: archetypical interactions, illustrative scenarios, design scenarios, presentation scenarios, mockups, experimental settings, generic test suites, and documentation scenarios.

Presentation scenarios, in particular, are easily displayed using storyboards and video, providing audiences with the entire picture related to the products depicted. Presentation scenarios were also the inspiration for this teaching experiment and related research.

EXPERIENCE DESIGN AND EMOTIONAL DESIGN

Pi-Fen Huang (2005) described how designers are unable to fulfill user demands without referring to the elements of knowledge, emotions, aesthetics, and spiritual and cultural needs. Huang believes that an emotional connection is created through creativity (aesthetics), context (life experience, unusual events and situations), content (theme), and

results (stirred-up emotions, encouraged thinking). Huang also listed the four factors that distinguish experience design from traditional design: (1) expected results; (2) memories of wonderful moments; (3) story-telling; and (4) sharing.

The Starbucks coffee chain is a good example of experience design. Schultz & Yang (2000), the author of "Starbucks Coffee Kingdom of Legends", analyzed the strategy of enticing customers with the full range of their five senses, taste, smell, hearing (playing Jazz, blues or classical music, even the noise of coffee machines), sight (the style of the decor), and touch (texture of wood). To capture a good memory and story for their customers, Starbucks in Taiwan even provides a notebook for messages in every store, resulting in interesting graffiti and messages left by customers.

Experience design and emotional design are linked to the plot of the story, which are in turn closely related to the usage and image of products. For this reason, we adopted the plot of stories related to products as the basis with which to teach visual stories.

AESTHETICS OF RECEPTION AND UNDERSTANDING SCOPE

Literary critics have traditionally employed a triangular model in literature, comprising the author, the work, and the general public. This theory can also be applied in product design in which the triangle comprises: the designer, the product, and the general public. Since the emergence of Reception Theory, the focus has shifted to a reader-centered, rather than author-centered or text-centered approach. The psychology of audiences (or product users) has assumed value. The way that users think, how they interpret the story and the means to impress them and create in them an emotional response have become issues of considerable importance.

In his book, "The Psychology of Audiences", Yu (2006) quoted the Understanding Scope theory from Hans Robert Jauss. Yu believes the aggressive participation of recipients enriches the spiritual life of art works. When the recipient views the art work,

his mind is not a psychological vacuum, but rather has already been structured by aesthetic experience and life within society. The same is true for product design. Based on their life experiences, potential users may be impressed by the visual story and experience a more profound interpretation of the advertisement.

RESEARCH METHOD

TEACHING EXPERIMENT

The subjects of this teaching experiment comprised an experimental group (22 students) and control group (19 students). The participants were college students in design majors. The experimental group was asked to attend a six-week course on visual storyness in design, including visual narration theory, case studies, working with visual story-making reference cards, and one-to-one instruction. The remainder of the subjects received the normal training provided in the design course. The teaching materials used in the course on visual storyness in design were inherited from a previous paper by the author. These included the features of visual storyness in design, including eight categories of visual composition and five categories of emotional response. To evaluate differences between the two groups in their final performance as well as the effectiveness of the teaching experiment, we adopted a teaching satisfaction scale, peer assessment, and consensus assessment.

DESIGN OF EXPERIMENT

The relationship between dependent, independent, and controlled variables are explained in the following:

- Dependent variable: Differences in design performance.
- Independent variable: Teaching experiment.

- Controlled variables: the number of teaching hours in the course, student background, equipment, instructor, the location of the experiment and the brand of products on which projects are based.

TEACHING MATERIALS FOR EXPERIMENTAL GROUP

In this experiment, we established a creation training module in which students were asked to implement a solution by filling out story-making reference cards. The cards (see Table 1) were divided into two parts, an upper part, a reference area created by the author, and a bottom part “thinking and creation area” to be filled out by students. The first two rows in the thinking and creation area dealt with visual composition and emotional response derived from features of visual storyness provided by the author. Porcelain products from the Franz Company were selected by participants to be featured in ads.

VISUAL STORYNESS FEATURES

The visual storyness features included aspects of visual composition as well as those of emotional response. The eight categories of visual composition included: (1) gesture and eye-contact of main character; (2) diary or scrawling text; (3) a hint of story background; (4) the obviousness of theme; (5) dramatic and imaginary space; (6) fairy tale and reminiscence; (7) contrast or special layout; and (8) numerous clues and dialogue box. The emotional response of readers to the storyness is summarized as follows: (A) positive affection; (B) awe and familiarity; (C) expectation of outcome, (D) plot, (E) perceived message. These features of visual storyness are the core criteria to be followed when students create visual storyness in advertisements.

No.1 : The Application of Fairytale				
Refer- ence Area		visual composition	(6) fairy tale and reminiscence	
		emotional response	(A) positive affection (B) awe and familiarity	
		event in ad	Pinocchio looks at the floor (the product in the ads), the background includes an old man reading in front of a wood stove and warm atmosphere.	

		copy	Whilst knowing full well that the beautiful floor was Mohawk laminate, Pinocchio couldn't help telling people it was real wood.
Thinking and Creation Area		visual composition	(6) fairy tale and reminiscence (1) gesture and eye-contact of main character
		emotional response	(B) awe and familiarity (D) plot
		event in ad	The queen asked the magic mirror: What is the most beautiful thing in the world? The answer is a china vase instead of Snow White, who is shown in the bottom right corner and is shocked to hear this.
		copy	"The magic mirror tells the truth."

Table 1. Example of story-making reference card

STORY-MAKING REFERENCE CARD

A story-making reference card is presented in Table 1. The bottom part, Thinking and Creation Area, is filled out by the student who created the ad named "The magic mirror tells the truth" in promoting a Franz vase.

CASE STUDY: VISUALLY NARRATED STORY ADS FOR AMERICAN EXPRESS CREDIT CARD AND KOHLER

The participants were also introduced to two case studies using scenarios in the real world, rather than having to rely only on theory.

One case was a serial ad for American Express credit card, in which celebrities were invited to talk about their thoughts, their dreams, the things they are proud of, as well as their relationship with the credit card (using hand-written script), instead of promoting the benefits of the product.

Another case was a series of ads for KOHLER, in which famous photographers were employed to create historical and cultural-like documentation by portraying the product (for example: washbowl, flush toilet, tub) as a treasure or antique in a dramatically-staged ad.

As Pink (2006) stated, "The typical person uses a toaster at most 15 minutes per day. The remaining 1425 minutes of the day the toaster is on display. In other words, 1 percent of the toaster's time is devoted to utility, while 99 percent is devoted to

significance." The significance of dialogue and documentation in everyday life and culture in ads make these products count. This is the reason we selected these ads to support our emphasis on the visual narration of stories in ads.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

PEER ASSESSMENT

After undergoing creative training, the experimental group underwent peer assessment in which every participant voted for the best projects featuring a strong sense of visual storyness. The top 3 students were awarded prizes.

TEACHING SATISFACTION SCALE

A 7-level Likert scale of teaching satisfaction was adopted from the scale used in the field of academic education, and modified for this experiment. Reliability analysis of the scale was evaluated using Cronbach's α of 0.8144(>0.7) demonstrating that internal consistency was high. Finally, the average of the teaching satisfaction scale was calculated and the results are shown in the following table:

Item	average	Cronbach's α if-item-deleted	Cronbach's α
I found this learning experience interesting.	5.00	.832	.814

I think the reference materials in this course are adequate.	4.86	.841
I don't think this course will be helpful to my abilities in graphics or advertisement design.	5.19	.837
I am satisfied with the one-on-one instruction.	4.81	.806
I am satisfied with the freedom and flexibility of learning.	4.81	.833
I am satisfied with the teaching	4.86	.818
I am satisfied with the learning environment.	4.81	.839
I am satisfied with the overall learning effectiveness of this course.	5.00	.788

Table 2. Average and internal consistency of teaching satisfaction scale

The average in Table 2 exceeded 4 points, indicating that students were satisfied with the teaching experiment.

CONSENSUS ASSESSMENT

Evaluation is a scientific method of collecting data on student learning behavior and achievement, followed by analysis to judge the performance according to teaching goals (Chien, 1997). Consensus Assessment Techniques, developed by Amabile in 1983, are based on natural human creativity (Zhang, 2002). Experts in a given field judge works according to the standards of uniqueness, value, and intuition.

Four design experts were invited to participate in the consensus assessment, to examine the strength of communication and emotional response conveyed by the design of the ads. It included six items with a 7-level Likert scale. A t-test was then used to compare the experimental and control group, and the results are as follows:

Item	Subjects	Average	SD	t-value	Significance
Perception	Experimental	4.55	.76	-2.180	.035

	group				
Understanding	Control group	3.98	.91	-2.089	.043
	Experimental group	4.21	.68		
Association	Control group	3.65	.99	-3.298	.002
	Experimental group	4.34	.72		
Emotion	Control group	3.57	.95	-3.155	.003
	Experimental group	4.41	.71		
Persuading	Control group	3.42	.93	-2.022	.050
	Experimental group	3.95	.71		
Behavior	Control group	3.41	.94	-.709	.482
	Experimental group	3.59	.67		

Table 3. Summary of independent t-test on consensus assessment of "advertisement communication and emotional response"

In Table 3, we can see that the average performance of the experimental group (regarding the emotional response triggered by their designs) is significantly higher than that of the control group. On the item "Behavior", the average was higher too; however, the difference is not significant ($p = .482 > 0.05$), as the probability of committing a Type I statistical error is 0.05.

The lack of a significant difference in the "Behavior" item may be explained by the theory of the Consumer Black Box model, in which Kotler (1997) claimed that what takes place in the "black box" of the consumer mind is a complex process, involving the interaction of stimuli, consumer characteristics, and consumer responses. The result of the independent t-test appears to be in accord with Kotler's theory.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on the knowledge of emotional design, scenarios, and the psychology of reader response, this research attempted to help young designers to create visual stories in ads. This was accomplished

through an explanation of narration theory, case studies, and the practical application of tips in story-making using reference cards, as well as one-to-one instruction. We adopted the research method of a teaching experiment as well as consensus assessment techniques, and learning satisfaction evaluation, proving that the students in the experiment performed better in most of the criteria for “the communication and emotion reaction to ads” over that of the control students. The criteria included perception, understanding, association, emotion, persuasion, and behavior. Significant differences appeared in an independent t-test for all of the criteria except “Behavior”, which may be due to the consumer black box model.

The results of the teaching experiment and creative design tips proved to be helpful for these college students majoring in design, aiding them in their presentation of visual storyness both in product design procedures and advertisement images, as a means to impress audiences/message receivers with an interesting and unique experience.

Because of the limitations of time, space, and funding, the scope of project was limited with regard to the number of subjects and design experts. Preliminary results from the rating scale of

advertisement communication and emotion reaction require further analysis to prove internal consistency and reliability.

REFERENCES

- Chien, M. F. (1997) *Psychological testing and statistical methods*. Taipei: Psychology
- Huang, M. F. (2005) *A study of experience design*. Master Dissertation. National Yunlin University of Science and Technology, Taiwan.
- Jensen, R. translated by Chen, R.W. (2000) *The dream society : how the coming shift from information to imagination will transform your business*. Taipei: McGraw-Hill Education.
- Kotler, P., (1997) *Marketing Management*”, 9th ed, New York, NY: McGraw-Hill Co..
- Nielsen, J. (1990) Paper versus computer implementations as mockup scenarios for heuristic evaluation. In proceedings of INTERACT.
- Norman, D. A. (2004) *Emotional design*. New York, NY: Basic Books.
- Pink, D. H. (2006) *A whole new mind: moving from the Information Age to the Conceptual Age*. New York, NY: Riverhead Books.
- Schultz, H. & Yang, D. J. translated by Han, H.T. (2000). *Pour your heart into it : how Starbucks built a company one cup at a time*. Taipei: Linkbooks .
- Tang, T. T. & Kang, S. C. (2008) *Scenario, User-oriented innovative design(UOID)*, retrieved on Feb, 11. 2011 from <http://uoid.drhtang.net/Home>
- Yu, C. Y. (2006) *The psychology of the audiences*. Taipei: Bookzone.